

Identifying Territory-linked Family Business Groups: A methodological proposal

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to design a methodology to identify territory-linked family business groups (TLFBGs) in order to overcome the methodological challenges and ease studies about family business groups' (FBGs) impact on territories.

Design/methodology/approach: The paper applies an algorithm to a dataset of firms located in Gipuzkoa that were registered in the SABI database in 2018.

Findings: The paper defined a new construct, TLFBGs, and proposed a methodology that automatized the identification of TLFBGs by a seven-stage algorithm that was intended to be applicable to any firm-level economic and financial data set, including all registered firms and not only listed firms.

Practical implications: TLFBG unveils the real relevance that family businesses have in the territorial development, encouraging the political support to family business. Additionally, the methodology provided allows understanding growth processes of family business.

Originality/value: The paper defines a new construct, TLFBGs, that highlights both the underexplored links existing between family and territory and between family and business groups, providing the process and criteria to capture it. The paper opens up large-scale empirical research on the social (and economic) influence of TLFBG in territorial development.

Keywords: family business, family business groups, territory, algorithm, ownership control

1. Introduction

As Steier *et al.* (2015) note, a large part of the literature on family firms has implicitly assumed that the owning family has a single business, and thus, the family firm has been the preferred unit of analysis. However, as time passes, businesses and families both evolve, and they often accumulate other assets, some within the firm and some outside it, pointing to a mode of strategic decision-making by the family (Carney and Nason 2018). These authors join others who also find that business families own a portfolio of firms over the course of their histories (Sieger *et al.*, 2011; Zellweger *et al.*, 2012, among others) and even gradually liquidate ownership positions in the founding firm (Akhter *et al.*, 2016; Franks *et al.*, 2012).

Choi *et al.* (2015) stated that as long as family owners create or acquire more affiliates and form a larger family business group, they are more likely to reach their family control goals. The dynamics within the family (Carter and Ram, 2003; Sirmon and Hitt, 2003), the family's long-term perspective (Miller and Le Breton-Miller, 2005) and, specifically, the family's need to diversify risk, generate income opportunities, and secure employment for family members (Carter and Ram, 2003), affect their resources, strategies and approaches and, therefore, condition the emergence, development and morphology of family business groups. These findings reveal an economical rationality where asset allocation decisions are optimized on the household level rather than on the firm level. The accumulated family wealth is no longer isolated in a single business but is reallocated over time beyond a focal firm to achieve dynastic wealth goals (Carney and Nason 2018); therefore, families typically extend their influence beyond the single founding business.

Moreover, the literature has defined the construct of entrepreneurial families, understood as institutions or social structures with certain characteristics that can facilitate or constrain entrepreneurial activities, processes and outcomes (Nordqvist and Melin 2010). Research within the family business field has recognized the impact of entrepreneurial families in territories (Carney and Nason 2018; Le Breton-Miller and Miller 2018; Nordqvist and Melin 2010) and *vice versa* (Chirapanda, 2019). Indeed, entrepreneurs and their families are the "creative soul" of a territory with which they are intimately linked and in which they reinvest part of the economic wealth they generated as well as their energies (Del Baldo 2012). Families can be subjects of the so-called "entrepreneurial recycling" (DeTienne 2010) process when family members have a positive impact on local and regional development. If territories become hostile to entrepreneurial families, family members can decide to relocate their entrepreneurial projects elsewhere (Gómez *et al.*, 2018). Despite the acknowledgement of the impact of family businesses on regions (Stough *et al.*, 2015; Bird and Wennberg, 2014; Block and Spiegel, 2013), knowledge about families, family business groups

and their role in the regions where they are located is very limited (Steier *et al.*, 2015; Konsti-Lakso *et al.*, 2019).

The methodological challenges of researching family business groups have made it difficult to conduct studies about their impact on territories. As Rosa *et al.* (2019, p.38-39) state, “accessing and constructing quantitative databases suitable for the statistical analysis of family business groups is difficult, time-consuming and expensive. Unlike researching single businesses or firms, there are no national or other large-scale databases where the unit of analysis is the business group, rather than the single firm”. Given these challenges, the case-study method has mainly been used to explore family business groups, normally based on one (Michael-Tsabari *et al.*, 2014; Rautiainen *et al.*, 2010) or more case studies (Akhter *et al.*, 2016; Alsos *et al.*, 2014; Manikutty, 2000; Sieger *et al.*, 2011) and where convenience is the main criterion used for case selection. Thus, there is a need to develop quantitative empirical research on this subject, despite the abovementioned challenges. Very few studies are grounded in databases of family business groups, though one such example is Masulis *et al.* (2011). These authors illustrate the difficulties and expense of constructing a meaningful database of family business groups, and their study constitutes the most rigorous attempt using international secondary data. However, our methodological proposal aims to go slightly beyond that. First, the present paper includes all registered firms and not only listed firms, aiming to achieve a more representative image of the relevance of the family business groups in a given territory; second, not only the control but also the non-control shareholdings belonging to the family are included in the analysis, which is another attempt to more faithfully represent the families’ impact on the fabric of territorial businesses; third, the identification as *family* business groups is based on kinship relationships among either shareholders or members of the Board of Directors of the group’s companies, and it does not assume that firms owned by a single individual owner are family firms.

Therefore, the present paper pursues the identification of territory-linked family business groups (TLFBGs), understood as the collection of businesses whose headquarters’ registered offices are located in a specific territory linked to a family through control or non-control ownership relationships. This paper defines an automated algorithm that is able to identify these TLFBGs from firm-level datasets available in secondary databases.

Our contribution is threefold. First, the paper makes the TLFBG an operational and feasible unit of analysis for quantitative studies that depart from a firm-level dataset. The proposed automated algorithm can build a complete profile of the families’ business groups, which allows us to quantitatively explore, beyond the

traditional family-firm unit, the construct of business families. Moreover, the paper addresses the identification of family-owned business groups whose governance is linked to the territory, which has not yet been addressed by quantitative empirical studies. Second, the proposed algorithm embodies several methodological improvements to the identification of the family nature of these business groups and thus the construction of family business groups, adopting a broader conception that includes businesses that belong to the group but in which families are not the main shareholders. Third, the paper integrates the territorial approach in the study of family business groups, allowing future analysis of entrepreneurial families' influence in the development of business activities in a given territory and contributing to the family entrepreneurship field (Bettinelli *et al.*, 2014), opening up new avenues for designing large-scale empirical research that may contribute to the understanding of the role of family business groups in territorial development.

The section following this introduction describes the previous literature on the subject. Section three presents the seven-step algorithm that automatizes the identification of TLFBG out of any firm-level economic and financial dataset and its application to a specific dataset of firms located in Gipuzkoa extracted from the SABI database in 2018. In section four, some robustness tests are presented, and finally, section five is devoted to the conclusions and future lines of research.

2. The identification of TLFBG: Main challenges

As Rautiainen *et al.* (2010) point out, the traditional family-firm unit of analysis oversimplifies the real complexity of family ownership, as families are owners of complex sets of businesses. Moreover, family control goals are better protected in the business group structure than in the independent firm structure, as business groups often engage in cross-subsidization to help unprofitable affiliates (Ferris *et al.*, 2003; George and Kabir, 2008) by, for example, providing loans or guarantees (Estrin *et al.*, 2009). One of these goals is continuity. Indeed, it is widely accepted that families are interested in passing on their legacy “in a manner that is potentially sustainable” (Chua *et al.*, 1999, p. 25), which implies a continuity that should lead to both an entrepreneurial and investment project (Gallo *et al.*, 2004) that is maintained over time through a diversity of business initiatives undertaken by the entrepreneurial family (Basco *et al.*, 2018).

However, definitions of business groups, family business groups, family-controlled business groups, and family portfolios are intertwined in the literature. Some authors use broad definitions that encompass both family and non-family groups. One example is Granovetter (2010), who defined a business group as a

collection of legally independent entities bound by formal or informal ties. Other authors focus on family business groups. Fisman and Khanna (2004), for instance, defined family business groups as a set of businesses, often initiated by a single family, and bound together by equity cross ownership and common board membership. In this sense, Sieger *et al.* (2011) point out that portfolio entrepreneurship is particularly relevant in family firms, and for instance, when family business owners decide to invest abroad (Filatotchev *et al.*, 2007), diversify risk, or explore growth opportunities, they opt for a low equity stake in an affiliate to support its business legacy in the long run. In general, the focus of these definitions on the family's control over firms is useful to distinguish family business groups from other business groups. However, reliable representation of these family business groups should also include companies in which the family is not the main shareholder. Based on this rationale, we define the family business group concept as a set of firms linked by both controlling and non-controlling ownership relationships, where the ultimate owner is a family.

Additionally, when embedded in the territory, entrepreneurial families' strong ties with their communities may produce reciprocal positive effects (Le Breton-Miller and Miller, 2009; Niehm *et al.*, 2008); they not only persevere and financially boost their communities when difficulties arise but also aim to maintain their legacy, which is rooted and tied to future generations. From this point of view, contrary to what is commonly argued in the field (e.g., Niedermeyer *et al.*, 2010), divesting or closing firms in a given territory may be a valuable activity from the entrepreneurial family's perspective (Zellweger *et al.*, 2012). Regarding the territory-linked characteristic, and despite the potential of related concepts, such as family firms' embeddedness, or the concept of proximity to the territory, quantitative studies have not operationalized these concepts by applying them to business groups. We call TLFBGs a first attempt to operationalize the link between family business groups and territories, in order to allow future studies to deepen these concepts for large-scale quantitative datasets. Therefore, in this paper, we conceptualize TLFBGs as a set of firms linked by both controlling and non-controlling ownership relationships, where the ultimate owner is a family located in the territory of interest. Despite the relevance of family ownership, as Rosa *et al.* (2019) state, the current state of research into family business groups is one where relevant research questions are being identified but where researchers must overcome serious methodological challenges to conduct meaningful empirical studies.

First, these challenges address the operationalization of the family business group concept and specifically the concept of TLFBGs. When we talk about family business groups, we are referring to the level of family control over the business belonging to the group. Authors such as Chang and Hong (2002), Morck and Yeung (2003) and Mahmood and Lee (2005) include the family control requirement in their definition of business groups. They defined business groups as a collection of formally independent firms under the administrative and financial control of certain families. In those cases, studies are limited to the set of firms over which families exert control relationships, in other words, where the family is the main shareholder. Later, Masulis *et al.* (2011) considered family business groups as a collection of firms connected through direct, pyramidal, and/or cross-holding ownership tied to a common ultimate owner, a family or an individual who maintains control relationships over them. Interestingly, Zhu and Chung (2014) analysed the top business groups in Taiwan, with at least three independent firms that achieve more than NT\$5 billion in total sales, and where more than 51 percent of ownership belongs to an entrepreneur. These cases, given their focus on governance issues, do not encompass the complete reality of the families' owned businesses; they are concerned with the firms over which the family exerts control, leaving out the study of other investments where the families have non-control stakes. In this sense, the control-ownership chains for each firm has a final controlling shareholder, that is, the *global owner* of the firm, that can be a firm or an individual. In this paper we define the global owner as the final controlling shareholder of this ownership chain that is composed of main-holding links that are larger than 25% of the participating firm capital. In family business groups the global owner is the family or the family-controlled company that heads and controls the group.

A second challenge is capturing the familial nature of the business group by identifying a family as the global owner of the business group, which implies that beyond identifying the individual owners of the parent firms, a family structure also has to be identified. Case-study based research on family groups or portfolios (Akhter *et al.*, 2016; Alsos *et al.*, 2014; Manikutty, 2000; Michael-Tsabari *et al.*, 2014; Rautiainen *et al.*, 2010; Sieger *et al.*, 2011, among others) allows a fine-grained identification of the family involved throughout the business group. However, in quantitative studies, capturing the familial nature of the business group is more complex and has been worked out differently. For example, in Masulis *et al.* (2011), the groups where an individual owner was behind the group were directly considered family business groups. As aforementioned, the more sophisticated intent – i.e., to capture the familial nature of these groups – comes from qualitative research, where both family equity holding and family involvement

in governance or management are criteria used to identify family groups. For example, Manikutty (2000) establishes criteria such as the equity holding of the family (more than 15% in the topmost-level company in the group), the family presence in the position of CEO and other managerial positions (at least two family members) and family members on the Board of Directors (at least two members). Additional criteria in the case-study-based research, are self-perception as a family business, dimensions of the main operating business and the ambition to pass on the business to the next generation (Nordqvist and Zellweger, 2010). Inspired by these previous attempts and attending to the limitations of working with firm-level databases, this paper goes beyond previous quantitative studies. Unlike those studies, this paper addresses the challenge of identifying the family nature of a business group by looking for kinship relationships referenced in public databases among either shareholders or members of the Board of Directors.

Therefore, the paper tries to address the mentioned challenges by defining a seven-step methodology that identifies TLFBG where control and non-controlled ownership investments are included and whose ownership is linked to a territory of study. This attempt indeed aims to help researchers developing quantitative studies on the contribution of families to territorial development and entrepreneurial dynamics.

3. A seven-step method for identifying TLFBGs

The proposed methodology automatizes the identification of TLFBGs by a seven-stage algorithm that is intended to be applicable to any firm-level economic and financial dataset. This algorithm has been applied to a dataset of firms located in Gipuzkoa that were registered in the SABI database in 2018. This application resulted in the identification of a total of 253 TLFBGs rooted in Gipuzkoa. These TLFBGs represent 31.2% of the total 811 business groups linked to this territory, and they comprise a total of 957 subsidiary firms, 26.2% of the total 3,653 subsidiary firms involved in the 811 business groups linked to this territory.

3.1. First step: Firm-level database standardization

Firm-level ownership, subsidiaries and financial data were obtained from the Spanish SABI database. This database has been widely used in other empirical studies on family firms (Dieguez-Soto *et al.*, 2015; Sacristán-Navarro *et al.*, 2011; among others). Specifically, we used the data available in December 2018. Based on this database, we have constructed two different datasets, the *firm dataset* and the *control-ownership-links dataset*. The firm dataset includes all the different firms that appear throughout the different sections of the database (main firms, subsidiaries, shareholders, global owners, etc.). For each firm, we have gathered all the available information about its identification code, name, country, region,

incorporation date, employees and activity sector, among other variables. This dataset includes firms of different nationalities. The control-ownership dataset is composed of all shareholding participations that any individual or firm has over any other firm. To build this dataset, we compiled all the stockholdings included in the database that contain information on shareholders, subsidiaries and global owners, erasing duplicates. For each direct stake, we have collected information about the participating firm, the shareholder's name and identification code, the percentage of shareholding and the type of shareholder involved (an individual or a firm). For the purpose of this paper, in this second dataset, we have selected only the main shareholders' stakes that are larger than 25% of the participating firm capital. To understand the reason for this threshold, it is important to take into account that global owners' SABI database are calculated considering only main shareholdings of more than 25%. For this reason, we have fixed the minimum threshold for the links of the control-ownership chains at this level. Consequently, among all the shareholdings we have identified, we have selected those that correspond to main shareholders and are larger than 25%.

3.2. Second Stage: Building the control-ownership chains

The aim of this stage is to build the control-ownership chains for each firm included in the firm dataset to identify the final controlling shareholder, that is, the *global owner* of the firm. Through an iterative process, and making use of all available shareholding data, we have built for each company the entire chain of control of the property until it reaches its final owner. At the end of this process, all the companies belonging to the same global owner and forming a business control group are identified. The business control group is the set of companies that are linked through ownership control links to the same global owner.

3.3. Third Stage: Sample selection and typing firm-level ownership structures

The developed algorithm has been applied to a dataset extracted from SABI and composed of firms located in Gipuzkoa. The territory of Gipuzkoa is selected for this exploration because the authors' knowledge about business families in this territory and their access to relevant experts is needed to evaluate the accuracy and robustness of the TLFBG identification algorithm.

From the total number of firms located in Gipuzkoa, according to the mentioned firms' dataset 22,858 firms, only 17,829 firms are qualified as active firms. Companies not qualified as "active" were excluded from our sample^[1]. Ultimately, 9,814 firms compose the final sample, all of which are located in Gipuzkoa (Spain) and have ownership and/or subsidiaries data available.

Once the sample has been selected, each company is typified regarding its ownership structure. The distribution of the sample among the different types of firm-level ownership structures is presented in Table I. As Table I shows, 69% of the firms of the sample do not belong to any business group, so they are single firms, and only firms in types 3, 4, 5 and 6 belong to a business group (31% of the sample).

<Insert Table I here.>

3.4. Fourth Stage: Identifying the control-business groups

In this stage, the control-business groups are identified. Firms belonging to types 3, 4, 5 and 6 are analysed and grouped together with those who share the same global owner, identifying the existing business groups. We must underline that the business groups include all firms that are under the control of the identified global owner; therefore, the complete portfolio of investments owned by each global owner (including non-controlled subsidiaries) is expected to be larger than the identified control-business group.

<Insert Table II here.>

Behind the 3,046 firms located in Gipuzkoa that belong to a business group (types 3, 4, 5 and 6), as Table II shows, we have identified 1,289 different business groups. Most of these business groups (67.7%) are controlled by a global owner that is another company that, according to our available data, is not controlled by any other shareholder (firm or individual) with a participation greater than 25% of the capital. In addition, 32.3% of the identified control-business groups have an individual as a global owner. It is important to emphasize that both businesses and individuals who have been classified as global owners can be located anywhere in the world.

3.5. Fifth stage: Territory-linked control-business groups

We have considered that territory-linked business groups are those whose registered office address is located in the territory of the study and geographical information about the global owner of the business group is used to classify a business group as territory-linked.

When the geographical origin of the global owner is not available, the geographical information of the first-level subsidiaries controlled directly by the global owner is analysed. When some data about the geographical location of the direct subsidiaries are missing, the algorithm qualifies a business group as territory-linked if more than 50% of the assets of the directly controlled subsidiaries are located in the territory of the study.

<Insert Table III here.>

Table III shows that most of the global owners, 63% (811 out of 1,289), are from Gipuzkoa. Of these, 63.4% are businesses and 36.6% are individuals linked to this territory. Moreover, 21.9% of the global owners are from other Spanish regions, and the remaining 15.1% are tied to foreign countries. Business groups linked to the territory of Gipuzkoa account for 3,653 of the total 9,814 active firms in this territory (37.2%).

3.6. Sixth Stage: Identifying territory-linked family control-business groups

With the aim of identifying family control-business groups, kinship relationships among either shareholders or members of the Board of Directors must be found, and thus, surnames of all stakeholders involved in the ownership structure and surnames of all members of the Board of Directors are taken into account. The kinship relationship between owners and directors has also been considered in Perez-Gonzalez (2006), and the relationship between CEO and owners has been used as a family status criterion in Gomez-Mejia (2001), where the coincidence of the last name is the requirement to be considered familiar.

In our case, when looking for family ties, we took advantage of the Spanish custom of giving children two surnames, one from each parent. Therefore, beyond the existence of an individual as the global owner of the business group, evidence of kinship relationships must be found to identify a business group as a family group. Depending on the type of global owner of the business group, the algorithm will operationalize this requirement following different paths:

- Business groups with an individual or a family as global owner. In those cases, the familial nature is identified if at least one coincidence is found when comparing each one of the surnames of this individual global owner with the surnames of any of the shareholders or members of the Board of Directors of any of the firms belonging to the business group. A total of 245 family-controlled business groups were identified in the sample.
- Business groups with a firm as global owner. In those cases, the familial nature is identified if there are two or more individual shareholders with the same surname who control more than 25% of the capital of the firm that is the global owner of the group. A total of 8 family-controlled business groups were identified in the sample.

The conditions established in the algorithm result in classifying as non-family groups those groups whose global owners are individuals. Specifically, we have identified 52 Gipuzkoan individuals who are global

owners of non-family groups since they do not meet the kinship requirements to be typified as family groups.

<Insert Table IV here.>

The result of this process of classifying territory-linked control-business groups according to their family nature (Table IV) shows that we have identified 253 family business groups linked to the territory of Gipuzkoa that control 957 subsidiaries that can be found all around the world. This represents 31.2% of the total number of control business groups linked to the territory identified in Gipuzkoa. Most of them (245 out of 253) have an individual as a global owner of the family business group.

At this stage we assume that people within a firm with the same surname are from the same family. However, we acknowledge that surnames are very often linked to certain geographical areas and it may be that people who share the same surname do not share family links. In addition, it should be noted that the algorithm can be applied to a database offering a single surname, as is the case in many countries. Nevertheless, its ability to detect family ties will be lower because the comparison will be limited to a single surname.

3.7. Seventh Stage: Identifying TLFBG

In business groups, family control is usually strengthened through pyramidal and/or cross-shareholding ownership structures, which use indirect ownership to exert control over the firms belonging to the group (Almeida *et al.*, 2011). However, families not only have a controlling interest in the ownership of firms but may also hold minority shares in certain firms.

In this paper, we defined the family business groups as the collection of family-owned businesses linked by both control and non-control ownership relationships. Therefore, once we have the TLFBGs identified, we need to add the complete set of shareholdings that the owning family has obtained to build the global family-owned business group.

Specifically, at this stage, the identified TLFBGs are enriched by adding the participations in which the companies that make up the business group invest through direct shareholdings which, being greater than 5% are not made as main shareholder or, being between 5% and 25%, are made as main shareholder.

Overall, the identified 253 TLFBGs with global owners from Gipuzkoa hold 957 controlling shareholdings in companies that belong to their business groups and 84 additional noncontrolling stakes in firms that belong to their TLFBG.

<Insert Table V here.>

Table V shows that, on average, family business groups have fewer and smaller subsidiaries compared with non-family business groups. Additionally, non-family business groups have a larger number of non-controlling stakes than family business groups.

4. Testing the TLFBG identification algorithm

Due to the characteristics of the database used as the point of departure of the application of the algorithm and the decisions on the values of the parameters used in the different steps of the algorithm, it is estimated that the results obtained from the application of the algorithm will incur some errors. To assess the degree of accuracy and robustness of the algorithm, different tests have been performed to evaluate the accuracy of the algorithm addressing its two main challenges: the identification of the business groups linked to a given territory and, their characterization as family business groups.

4.1. Identification of business groups: sensitivity to ownership-chain threshold

The algorithm identifies business groups based on the construction of their ownership chains over a minimum ownership percentage of 25%. Obviously, we estimate that if the percentage of ownership required to identify control-ownership relations is reduced, the number of business groups identified by the algorithm would be higher. Table VI shows that, as expected, by lowering the threshold of the percentage of ownership required in the process of identifying business groups, the number of business groups identified also increases. By reducing from >25% to >20%, the number of groups identified increases by 7.9% and, from >20% to >15%, the number of groups increases by an additional 2.4%. Therefore, from > 25% to > 15%, only 85 new business groups have been identified with respect to the initial 811 groups (Table VI).

<Insert Table VI here.>

Moreover, as Table VI shows, not only the number of business groups increases as the minimum threshold required for the groups' shareholding chains decreases but also the weight of family groups identified increases in comparison to non-family business groups. When the family groups that at >25% have a company as a global owner (8 companies) change to >15%, they become groups with an individual/family as a global owner. Among these individual shareholders, there are kinship relationships that jointly give them participation greater than 25%, thereby granting the group a family character. When working with

>15% in the group identification process, at least one individual shareholder of these companies has participation that exceeds 15%, which makes him a global owner of the family group.

The percentage of TLFBG identified ranges from 31.2% to 34.4% of the total groups rooted in Gipuzkoa. There are no previous results regarding either this construct or this region. One of the few references we can find regarding family business groups in Spain is La Porta *et al.* (1999), who estimated that in the case of Medium-Sized Publicly Traded firms, family business groups represented 30% of the total business groups. Even if the ownership requirement was 20%, this rate is quite similar to ours (33.4%) with the same requirement. More recently, Masulis *et al.*, (2011) calculated that 50% of business groups were family business groups. This difference can be explained mainly by two reasons. First, because the definition of TLFBG used in this paper is more restrictive than the concept of family business group used by Masulis *et al.* (2011). Second, because of the type of company and the databases used, as Masulis *et al.* (2011) analyze larger companies with more information available on the family nature of the ultimate owner.

In our case, the restriction on information regarding the family nature of the owners implies a potential underestimation of the number of TLFBGs identified. This gap not only affects the identification of the business groups but also impacts the number of subsidiaries belonging to the TLFBG, which in our case represents 9.8% of the total firms of the sample. In Masulis *et al.*, (2011), the rate of subsidiaries belonging to family business groups is 11.6% out of the 164 total firms of the Spanish sample.

4.2. The robustness of the characterization of family business groups

Several contrasts have been performed to verify the robustness of the algorithm in identifying the family nature of the business groups identified.

First, for the family groups that have a Gipuzkoan individual as global owner, we check in the Spanish Family Business Institute's (IEF)² list whether the companies in which these individuals directly participate are classified as family businesses. The IEF has created an extensive database of Spanish family and non-family firms that has been used in this contrast. The result of this contrast shows that out of the 268 Spanish subsidiaries integrated into family groups that are controlled through direct participation by a Gipuzkoan individual global owner, a total of 112 are in the list of IEF companies. Of these, 109 companies are family businesses according to the IEF list, and only 3 companies are not classified as such. Therefore, 97.3% of the companies listed in the IEF list have been correctly classified as familiar by our algorithm (Table VII).

<Insert Table VII here.>

Second, for the family groups that have a Gipuzkoan company as global owner, we check the IEF list to determine whether these companies are classified as family businesses. The results show that of the 8 Gipuzkoan companies listed as global owners of family groups, 7 companies are listed as family businesses in the IEF list, and the other missing company does not appear on that list (Table VIII). Therefore, 100% of these companies that are part of the IEF list have been correctly classified as family members. For the latter mentioned companies controlled by the 8 companies that are global owners of family groups, a qualitative contrast was performed with experts who had extensive knowledge of the Gipuzkoan business landscape and with the firms themselves. The result of this revision is that 7 of these 8 confirmed that they are family groups. Only one of them considered itself a non-family group.

<Insert Table VIII here.>

In conclusion, the identification of the family nature of the business groups has proved to be accurate (Tables VII and VIII). However, we cannot assure that there may be more family business groups in the sample, because first, there are some companies that do not provide data on their shareholders and second, because the algorithm is not able to detect family ties that exist between shareholders who do not share any last names (for example, in the case of marriages).

5. Conclusions

The strategic decision making of entrepreneurial families can surpass the limits of the family firm because the firm may insufficiently diversify risk or take advantage of opportunities (Carter and Ram, 2003). Therefore, identifying TLFBG unlocks the family firm construct in favour of the business family that owns business groups, and it provides new possibilities to expand knowledge, such as measuring and generalizing group dimensions, configurations or features.

In this paper, following Das and Mukherjee (2006), we understand and embrace the complexity implied in the task of proposing a robust and automatized process for TLFBG operationalization. First, we propose a set of criteria along a sequence of steps for identifying TLFBGs. These criteria are based on the literature and have been tested to prove their robustness. Second, the process attempts to be self-sufficient and provides a completely automatized procedure. Thanks to these features, the first contribution is that this TLFBG identification process can be replicated by other researchers, assuring consistent results in terms of TLFBG identification, overcoming one of the main obstacles to the design of large-scale empirical studies on the issue.

Moreover, as a result of the application of this process, TLFBGs are identified based on three main characteristics. First, TLFBG includes dominating and not-dominating ownership links. This means that firms on which families exert minor control are considered part of the constellation of firms. Because of this approach, the composition of the group is more holistic, enriching family business research possibilities. Second, this approach distinguishes family groups from the rest of the business groups in a territory. Even though the difficulty of revealing family relationships remains a challenge, the strength of the possibilist criteria employed has been confirmed by the literature and the opinion of the experts surveyed. The identification of TLFBG may boost research on entrepreneurial families, as it provides a better unit of analysis to specifically capture the entrepreneurial behaviour of the significant stakeholder of family firms: the family (Zellweger *et al.*, 2012). Finally, the focus on the territory-linked characteristic, in other words, on family business groups related to a territory, provides the key to analysing entrepreneurial families' embeddedness in a territory.

Even if the automated algorithm proposed allows building and working with a large dataset of family groups, some limitations (regarding both the concept application and the database restrictions) are assumed in this contribution. On the one hand, the family is a changing concept that can include diverse configurations (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2019). Heterogeneous family members are part of an evolving and incomprehensible unity, the family, whose demographic lifecycle is dynamic; thus, a family can temporarily or permanently own a firm or a set of firms without sharing the same last name (Rosa *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, more than one family can be behind a business group, but the maximum number of families that can be involved in a family firm is unestablished. Furthermore, the specific nature of the use of both surnames in Spain, which is not very common in other countries, and the fact that within the same geographical area there are people who share surnames without sharing family links, may limit the accuracy of the proposed algorithm. The algorithm can be applied with databases that provide a single surname, although in these cases it must be taken into account that its ability to detect family ties is lower. In any case, these limitations could be overcome by questioning entrepreneurial families. The use of primary sources could refine, in a second step, the automated identification of family groups provided by the algorithm, removing cases that are not confirmed as family groups. Finally, the desire of the current owners for continuity regarding the business portfolio is not explicit, and thus, it has not been considered in the process.

On the other hand, database limitations involve restrictions, as the data registered do not fit with the specific requirements. Indeed, there are no data sources that provide detailed, specific information on business groups or family business groups (Rosa *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, to capture whether a person shares family links with others was particularly challenging. In this sense, the possibilistic approaches used in the literature remain disappointing as they fail capturing the desired reality. While brotherhood and parentality are approached through the last name coincidence of owners and members of the board of directors, neither all these links nor other possible links inside a family are captured in this proposal. In the same vein, all the firms connected in a business group are not identified and their ownership stakes are not quantified. For instance, firms located in other territories. Despite these limitations, the robustness tests performed help us to measure the accuracy of the algorithm presented.

As a result of these constraints and regarding the business groups, we can highlight that we do not capture either the family members' individual investment or the whole investment of the families that have more than one portfolio. Among the missing results related to family status, we admit that not all the family business groups are identified, however, all the FBGs identified are truly family groups. Indeed, the proposed methodology faces the difficulties and expenses of constructing a meaningful database of TLFBGs (Rosa *et al.*, 2019). Compared with Masulis *et al.*, (2011), the most rigorous and systematic attempt to use national secondary data to identify family business groups, our proposal allows, first, a more efficient replication, since it avoids extracting and integrating data from different sources, and second, it includes unlisted firms, not represented in Masulis *et al.* (2011).

In this research, we advance the study of family business groups, which is in its early stages, by accessing and constructing quantitative databases suitable for statistical analysis, as Rosa *et al.* (2019) propose. Regarding future research, new steps could be, first, to extend this methodology to other countries, as “family owners are the predominant type of controlling shareholders in many developing as well as in some of the most developed economies of the world” (Lozano and Duran, 2017, p. 267) and consider whether the concentration of control diminishes with the level of a country's development, as happens with firms (Claessens *et al.*, 2000). Second, as the proposed methodology involves both dominating and non-dominating ownership links, more complete TLFBG configurations could be studied, exploring the specific role that these non-control links play in the TLFBG.

Third, considering that family entrepreneurial teams are groups of related individuals who engage in entrepreneurship (Discua *et al.*, 2013), the employment of this unit of analysis would contribute to the

family entrepreneurship field (Bettinelli *et al.*, 2014), such as deepening in the diversity and autonomy of corporate entrepreneurial initiatives (Brumana *et al.*, 2017). Fourth, SEW could be analysed by family business groups. Finally, the paper opens up large-scale empirical research on the influence of TLFBG in territorial development and *vice versa* (Baù *et al.*, 2018).

Appendix

Table I. Distribution of firms located in Gipuzkoa in 2018 (number and %) by types of ownership structures

Types of ownership structures	Number of firms	%
Type 1. Firms with main ownership <25%	2,017	20.6%
Type 2. Firms with an individual as a controlling shareholder	4,751	48.4%
Type 3. Firms whose global owner is an individual or a family who also appear as global owners of other firms	536	5.5%
Type 4. Firms whose global owners are other firms	1,604	16.3%
Type 5. Matrixes of a business group. Companies that are global owners of other companies with more than 25% direct or indirect ownership, and no further details on their ownership.	593	6.0%
Type 6. Firms with several global owners.	313	3.2%
TOTAL	9,814	100%

Source: Own elaboration.

Table II. Control-business groups identified in Gipuzkoa (2018) by type of global owner

Type of global owner	Number	%
Business	873	67.7%
Individual	416	32.3%
Total	1,289	100%

Source: Own elaboration.

Table III. Business groups identified in Gipuzkoa (2018) by type of global owner and its geographic location

Type of global owner and its geographic location	Number	%
Global owner: business	873	67.7%
- Gipuzkoa	514	39.9%
- Others: Rest of Spain	181	14.0%
Foreign country	178	13.8%
Global owner: individual	416	32.3%
- Gipuzkoa	297	23.1%
- Others: Rest of Spain	102	7.9%
Foreign country	17	1.3%
Total	1,289	100%

Source: Own elaboration.

Table IV. Distribution of the territory-linked control-business groups by family nature

	Number of business groups	%	Number of controlled subsidiaries*	%
Family	253	31.2%	957	26.2%
- Global owner: business	8	1.0%	19	0.5%
- Global owner: individual	245	30.2%	938	25.7%
Non-family	558	68.8%	2,696	73.8%
- Global owner: business	506	62.4%	2,466	67.5%
- Global owner: individual	52	6.4%	230	6.3%
TOTAL	811	100%	3,653	100%

* These subsidiaries can be located in any country of the world.

Source: Own elaboration.

Table V. Size of the territory-linked family and non-family control-business groups and business groups

	Number of subsidiary firms* (Mean and StDev)	Total Assets of subsidiary firms (€, 2017) (Mean and StDev)	Total Assets of subsidiary firms/ Number of subsidiary firms (Mean and StDev)
Control-Business Groups	4.50 (23.91)	51,747,463 (540,875,606)	4,905,681 (12,722,593)
Family Control-Business Groups	3.78 (4.73)	20,317,806 (70,746,217)	3,309,441 (4,798,302)
Non-Family Control-Business Groups	4.83 (28.65)	67,187,663 (658,303,950)	5,689,853 (15,112,205)
Business Groups	5.06 (25.98)	61,937,142 (579,773,058)	5,181,405 (12,473,397)
Family Business Groups (TLFBG)	4.11 (5.66)	25,785,189 (104,749,418)	3,425,901 (5,061,706)
Non-Family Business Groups	5.49 (31.09)	79,560,348 (702,868,592)	6,037,172 (14,726,613)

* In Control-Business Groups, subsidiary firms are all the firms controlled by the global owner, and in Business Groups, subsidiary firms also include non-controlled firms.

Source: Own elaboration.

Table VI. Robustness test for territory-linked business groups identified in Gipuzkoa

	Number of business groups >25%	%	Number of business groups >20%	%	Number of business groups >15%	%
Family	253	31.2%	292	33.4%	308	34.4%
- Global owner: business	8	1.0%	2	0.2%	0	0%
- Global owner: individual	245	30.2%	290	33.2%	308	34.4%
Non-family	558	68.8%	583	66.6%	588	65.6%
- Global owner: business	506	62.4%	512	58.5%	513	57.2%
- Global owner: individual	52	6.4%	71	8.1%	75	8.4%
TOTAL	811	100%	875	100%	896	100%

Source: Own elaboration.

Table VII. Family business groups with individual global owners: Comparison with the IEF list

	Family Groups
Number of direct subsidiaries of the individual global owners identified by the algorithm	268
Number of direct subsidiaries of the individual global owners included in the IEF list (A)	112
Number of direct subsidiaries of the individual global owners included in the IEF list as family firms (B)	109
Algorithm error % (1-B/A)	2.7%

Source: Own elaboration.

Table VIII. Family business groups with a company global owner: Comparison with the IEF list

	Family Groups
Number of global owners (companies) in the business groups identified by the algorithm	8
Number of global owners (companies) included in the IEF list (A)	7
Number of global owners (companies) included in the IEF list as family firms (B)	7
Algorithm error % (1-B/A)	0%

Source: Own elaboration.

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¹ Firms of the following statuses were not included in the study: exit by trade, dissolved, in contest, extinguished, bankrupt, suspension of payments, and close registration form.

² The IEF is a non-profit, independent and private Spanish organization that includes more than one hundred family businesses, most of them leaders in their industries. Since its foundation in 1992, it has been an academic and business resource for family firms.